

Students' Perception on Negative Impacts of Social Media Use on Academic Performance in Colleges of Education in Osun State

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Abstract

The study focused on students' perception on negative impacts of social media use on academic performance in Colleges of Education in Osun State. Descriptive research design was adopted. The population of the study comprised 2,752 registered students in 2023/2024 academic session in the institutions, out of which 334 was proportionately sampled. Students' Perception on Negative Impacts of Social Media on Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (NISAPQ) was used to collect data for the study. Mean, standard deviation and ranking order were used to answer the research questions. The findings of the study revealed among others, that WhatsApp was the social media platform mostly used by students in Colleges of Education in Osun State. Chatting was the most reason students used social media in the institutions. Excessive use of social media for non-academic purposes could result in poor academic performance. Too much use of social media makes students lose concentration during lectures and this could consequently lead to poor academic performance. Students who frequently use social media do not utilise their leisure for self-study and this eventually causes poor academic performance. The study concluded that social media use had negative impacts on academic performance of students in Colleges of Education in Osun State. It was recommended that students should be committed to the use of social media for academic activities, rather than using it for frivolities, so as to enhance their academic performance.

Key words: Students, Perception, Social Media, Academic Performance, Colleges of Education

Introduction

Technological advancement has been seriously impacting economic, political, social, health and educational realms of not only Nigeria but also other countries. A country which does not maximally use the fortune of technological advancement is likely to lag behind in the comity of nations, in all ramifications. Technological advancement has compressed the entire world to a micro entity, where people at a distance of thousands of kilometers can interact as if they were sitting together in a meeting. Specifically, technological advancement has changed the narratives in educational milieu with the outbreak of different social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Wikipedia, Instagram, TikTok, LinkedIn and Snapchat. Through these platforms, teachers and students can perform different academic activities online.

According to Adeniyi (2022), social media means a group of online platforms which allow users to create contents, ventilate them around, bookmark them and link to one another at an amazing rate. Buettner (2016) defined social media as computer mediated gadgets which give people opportunity to create and exchange virtual communication, ideas, pictures, information, career information and network. Jimoh, Basiru, Salawu, Owonipa and Ibrahim (2021) elucidated academic performance as the measure of how a learner excels in the academic tasks given to him in an educational institution. Benjamin and Olayinka (2016) added that students' academic performance is the reflection of the level of success or failure which learners have made in a particular course of study. Shuaibu, Sani and Wada (2023) explained academic performance as how students handle their studies and how they carry out or complete different activities given to them by their teachers. Baharak, Ramli, Aminuddin and Asimiran (2017) saw academic performance as outcome of the level of success which students have made in a particular course of study, within a specified period of time. Tuten, Solomon and Ladik (2015) explained social media as the online methods of communication, collaboration, conveyance and cultivation with the use interdependent and interconnected networks of people, organizations and communities. According to Camilia, Ibrahim and Dalhatu (2013), the use of social media has been one of the most influential channels of communication which could be used to facilitate effective teaching and learning process. It provides students with the latitude to develop and share contents, comment on link and chat with friends as well as make new friends.

Ngwu (2021) observed that emergence of social media simplifies communication among human beings. Daniel, Rooselt and Hatley (2016) maintained that social media helps in improving

students' learning and academic performance, if properly utilised. Saheed (2022) argued that social media assists in facilitating effective teaching and learning. This is because the process and teaching and learning can take place at any time, unless physical classroom that is time-bound. Ali and Ahmad (2018) maintained that social media helps students to have access to different educational resources, allow them to learn at their own pace, provides them comfort and motivation and eventually helps in boosting their academic performance. Dada (2023) posited that social media does not only help in providing students with unlimited access to materials that could aid learning but also serve as an avenue which teaching and learning could take place to aid students' academic performance.

However, the manner in which many students are using it could have adverse effects on their academic performance. Osharvie (2015) maintained that the number of time which students spend on social media platforms is higher than what they utilise for academic activities. This could have negative influence of their academic performance. The study of Pantic, Damjanovic, Todorovic, Topalovic, Bojovic-Jovic, Ristic and Pantic (2018) found that extreme use of social media would have negative effects on academic performance of students and that the GPAs of students who devoted much time for social media were lower than that of their counterparts who did not.

As revealed by the study of Al-Rahmi and Othman (2018), social media use had a negative correlation with students' academic achievement. Extreme use of social media could lead to distraction, thereby causing reduction in devotion to academic engagement. Ali and Ahmad (2018) found in their study that too much use of social media could result in poor students' time management skills, thereby affecting their grades negatively. As discovered by Al-Rahmi and Zeki (2018), social media use could have positive and negative effects on academic performance of students, depending on how it is utilised. It further showed that students who purposely utilised social media for their academics had higher GPAs than those who did not use it for academic activities. The outcome of the study of Maya (2015) showed connectivity between the use of social media and low self-perceptions, lower academic performance, and less interest in college-oriented carriers. Adeniyi (2022) conducted a study on social media: negative effect on academic performance of secondary school students in Nigeria. Alarape and Abdulsamad (2020) examined the influence of social media on students' academic performance in polytechnics in Kwara State. Gabriel and Sunday (2021) conducted a study on assessment of the impacts of social media on students' academic performance in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State. Ngwu (2021) investigated the impact of social media on the academic performance of tertiary institution

students (A case study of Federal College of Education, Eha-Amufu). Haseena and Rasith (2016) found that the use of social media caused late submission of assignment, poor study habit, poor grammar spelling, and poor academic performance among students. Owusu and Agatha (2015) found that many students in Ghana who were enthralled in social media sites utilised it for downloading purposes and chatting with friends and this had negative effects on their academic performance. The finding of Agwi and Ogwueleka (2018) revealed that the time spent on social media sites had a significant relationship with students' academic performance. Also, the nature of activities engaged in by students on social media has a significant impact on their academic performance. The study of Samaila (2017) revealed that there was a significant negative influence of social media use on academic performance of students. The more students use of WhatsApp, the lower their academic performance.

Integration of social media into education system is a good development but the manner in which many students use it could be posing negative impacts on their academic performance. As observed by the researchers as well as the information gathered from some lecturers and students in Federal College of Education, Iwo, Osun State; Osun State of College of Education, Ila-Orangun and some other Colleges of Education in Nigeria, there has been indiscriminate use of social media among students. Some students do engage in chatting, watching films, streaming of live broadcast of social events, viewing pictures and videos on TikTok, Whatsapp, Instagram and the likes while lectures are ongoing. Not only that, the times that should be used for studying have been known for the time when many students are always busy on social media, with non-profitable activities to their learning. All these could be affecting students' academic performance negatively. However, many studies related to this present study had been conducted some researchers. For instance, However, none of the studies mentioned above focused on students' perception on negative impacts of social media use on academic performance in Colleges of Education in Osun State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to:

- i. Examine the social media platform mostly used by students in Colleges of Education in Osun State.
- ii. Determine the reasons students use social media in Colleges of Education in Osun State.
- iii. investigate the students' perception on negative impacts of social media use on their academic performance in Colleges of Education in Osun State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

- i. What is the social media platform mostly used by students in Colleges of Education in Osun State?
- ii. What are the reasons students use social media in Colleges of Education in Osun State?
- iii. What is the students' perception on the negative impacts of social media use on their academic performance in Colleges of Education in Osun State?

Methodology

The study focused on students' perception on negative impacts of social media use on academic performance in Colleges of Education in Osun State. It adopted descriptive research design. The scope of the study was limited to the Federal College of Education, Iwo and Osun State College of Education, Ila-Orangun which were the only public Colleges of Education in Osun State. All the 2,752 registered students in 2023/2024 academic session in the two institutions constituted the population of the study. Proportionate sampling technique was used to select 171 students out of the 1,410 in Federal College of Education, Iwo and 163 students out of the 1,342 in Osun State College of Education, Ila-Orangun, totaling a sample of 334, using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table for sample size determination. Students' Perception on Negative Impacts of Social Media Use on Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (NISAPQ) was used to collect data for the study. Three experts in the field of Educational Management validated the instrument by thoroughly checking the suitability of the items and as well their grammatical correctness. The researchers religiously checked and effected the corrections before the printing of the final copy used for data collection. Split-half method was used in ensuring reliability of the instrument. Thirty copies were administered to some students in Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin. The data gathered were subjected to analysis through the use of Cronbach's Alpha and reliability index of 0.75 was realised. This confirmed that the instrument was reliable to be used for the study. Likert-rating scale of Strongly Agree rated 4, Agree scored 3, Disagree assigned 2 and Strongly Disagree adjudged 1 was used for the instrument. The researchers and three students (research assistants) in each institution administered instrument to the respondents. Mean, standard deviation and ranking order were used to answer the research questions. Out of the 334 copies of the instruments, only 321 copies adequately filled and returned were used for analysis.

Results

Research question 1: What is the social media platform mostly used by students in Colleges of Education in Osun State?

Table 1

Social Media Platform Mostly Used by Students in Colleges of Education in Osun State

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Ranking
1.	Facebook	4.37	1.41	3 rd
2.	LinkedIn	1.22	0.45	10 th
3.	Twitter	3.05	1.21	5 th
4.	WhatsApp	4.71	1.62	1 st
5.	Instagram	3.53	1.39	4 th
6.	TikTok	4.46	1.51	2 nd
7.	YouTube	2.88	0.95	6 th
8.	Wikipedia	1.41	0.65	9 th
9.	Snapchat	2.83	0.90	7 th
10.	WeChat	2.77	0.64	8 th

Table 1 showed the social media platform mostly used by students in Colleges of Education in Osun State. As shown on the Table, WhatsApp, TikTok, Facebook, Instagram and Twitter had mean scores of 4.71, 4.46, 4.37, 3.53 and 3.05 respectively; and as such, ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th. Also, YouTube, Snapchat, WeChat, Wikipedia and LinkedIn had mean scores of 2.88, 2.83, 2.77, 1.41 and 1.22 respectively; hence, ranked 6th, 7th, 8th, 9th and 10th. Therefore, with the highest mean score of 4.71, the social media platform mostly used by students in Colleges of Education in Osun State was WhatsApp.

Research question 2: What are the reasons students use social media in Colleges of Education in Osun State?

Table 2

Reasons Students Use Social Media in Colleges of Education in Osun State

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Ranking
1.	Watching of films	3.97	1.31	3 rd
2.	Chatting with friends and family members	4.38	1.69	1 st
3.	Viewing of displayed pictures and videos	4.21	1.55	2 nd
4.	Listening to lectures related to their fields of study	1.05	0.42	9 th
5.	Reading of e-textbooks, news and other learning materials	1.21	0.66	8 th
6.	Correction of errors in their grammatical constructions	1.51	0.62	7 th
7.	Listening to music	3.22	1.37	5 th
8.		3.04	1.19	
9.	Betting	3.56	1.40	6 th
	Playing games			4 th

Table 2 showed the reasons students use social media in Colleges of Education in Osun State. As shown on the Table, chatting with friends and family members; viewing of displayed pictures and videos; listening to lectures related to their fields of study; watching of films; betting and playing games and listening to music had mean scores of 4.38, 4.21, 3.97, 3.56 and 3.22 respectively; hence, ranked 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th and 5th. Also, betting, correction of errors in their grammatical constructions, reading of e-textbooks, news and other learning materials and listening to lectures related to their fields of study had mean scores of 3.04, 1.51, 1.21 and 1.05 respectively; hence, ranked 6th, 7th, 8th and 9th.

Research question 3: What is the students' perception on negative impacts of social media use on their academic performance in Colleges of Education in Osun State?

Table 3

Negative Impacts of Social media Use on Students' Academic Performance in Colleges of Education in Osun State, Nigeria

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	Excessive use of social media for non-academic purposes could result in poor academic performance	4.11	1.52	Agree
2.	Too much use of social media makes students lose concentration during lectures and this could consequently lead to poor academic performance	4.44	1.79	Agree
3.	Students who frequently use social media do not have time for self-study and this eventually causes poor academic performance	4.32	1.41	Agree
4.	indiscriminate use of social media makes students waste most of their time on non-academic activities, thereby resulting in poor academic performance	3.99	1.28	Agree
5.	Excessive use of social media hinders students from properly preparing for examination; hence, poor academic performance	3.64	1.10	Agree
6.		3.11	0.98	
7.	Too much use of social media makes students skip lectures, thereby preparing ground for poor academic performance	2.96	.74	Agree
8.		3.55	1.20	
9.	Students who are always busy with social media may not like have time for assignments; hence, poor academic performance	1.31	0.44	Agree
	Indiscriminate use of social media prevents students from having time for tutorials and this could lead to poor academic performance			Agree
	Reasonable use of social media could lead to poor students' academic performance			Disagree

Table 3 showed the negative impacts of social media use on students' academic performance in Colleges of Education in Osun State. As shown on the Table, too much use of social media makes students lose concentration during lectures and this could consequently lead to poor academic performance; students who frequently use social media do not have time for self-study and this eventually causes poor academic performance; excessive use of social media for non-academic purposes could result in poor academic performance; and indiscriminate use of social media makes students waste most of their time on non-academic activities, thereby resulting in poor academic performance had mean scores of 4.44, 4.32, 4.11 and 3.99 respectively; hence, the decision taken on them was 'agree'. Excessive use of social media hinders students from properly preparing for examination; hence, poor academic performance; indiscriminate use of social media prevents students from having time for tutorials and this could lead to poor academic performance; too much use of social media makes students skip lectures, thereby preparing ground for poor academic performance; and students who are always busy with social media may not like have time for assignments; hence, poor academic performance had mean scores of 3.65, 3.55, 3.11 and 2.96 respectively; hence, the decision taken on them was 'agree'. Lastly, reasonable use of social media could lead to poor students' academic performance had a mean score of 1.31; hence the decision taken on it was 'disagree'.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that the social media platform mostly used by students in Colleges of Education in Osun State was WhatsApp. This finding agrees with the finding of Alarape and Abdulsamad (2020) which showed that WhatsApp was the most used social media platform among students in polytechnics in Kwara State. This finding is also in tandem with the finding of Gabriel and Sunday (2021) that the most commonly used social media among students in tertiary institutions in Kebbi State was WhatsApp.

The findings of the study showed that chatting with friends and family members was the most reason students used social media in Colleges of Education in Osun State. This finding corroborates the finding of Saheed (2022) which revealed that students mostly used social media for chatting friends in polytechnics in Benue State. In addition, this finding supports the position of Alarape and Abdulsamad (2020) that the use of social media is a welcome development in education, but it is a pity that many students mostly use it for chatting and other irrelevancies to their academic activities and this could affect their academic performance negatively.

The findings of the study showed that excessive use of social media for non-academic purposes could result in poor academic performance and too much use of social media makes students lose concentration during lectures and this could consequently lead to poor academic performance. Students who frequently use social media do not have time for self-study and this eventually causes poor academic performance; and indiscriminate use of social media makes students waste most of their time on non-academic activities, thereby resulting in poor academic performance. This finding supports the finding of Ali and Ahmad (2018) which found that that too much use of social media could result in poor students' time management skills, thereby affecting their grades negatively. The finding showed that excessive use of social media hinders students from properly preparing for examination; hence, poor academic performance. This finding supports the finding of Gabriel and Sunday (2021) that students who often use social media have poor concentration to learning; too much use of social media does not give students time to study well, students who are committed to the use of social media for non-academic activities do not attach much importance to learning; students with addiction to social media have not time for group discussion; hence, poor academic performance. The findings revealed that too much use of social media could make students skip lectures, thereby preparing ground for poor academic performance; and students who are always busy with social media may not likely have time for assignments; hence, poor academic performance. This finding agrees with Haseena and Rasith (2016) found that the use of social media caused late submission of assignment, poor study habit, poor grammar spelling, and poor academic performance among students. It was revealed through the findings that indiscriminate use of social media prevents students from having time for tutorials and this could lead to poor academic performance but reasonable use of social media would not lead to poor students' academic performance. This finding supports the finding of Al-Rahmi and Othman (2018) that social media use had a negative correlation with students' academic achievement. Extreme use of social media could lead to distraction, thereby causing reduction in devotion to academic engagement.

Conclusion

The study concluded that:

- i. WhatsApp was the social media platform mostly used by students in Colleges of Education in Osun State.

- ii. Chatting with friends and family members was the most reason students used social media in the institutions.
- iii. Social media use had negative impacts on students' academic performance in Colleges of Education in Osun State.

Recommendations

The study recommended that:

- i. Students should be committed to the use of social media for academic activities, rather than using it for frivolities, so as to enhance their academic performance.
- ii. College managements need to always organise orientation for new intakes and periodic and regular orientation should also be organised for all students on the negative impacts of social use on their academic performance.
- iii. Parents need to keep surveillance on their children, in order to ensure that they moderately and sensibly use social media, so as to prevent excessive use that could have negative impacts on their academic performance.
- iv. Lecturers should be vigilante while imparting knowledge to students to be able detect and also punish any students caught on social media, so as to serve a deterrent to others.

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